

Improving electrical energy efficiency through hydroelectric power and turbine optimization at the El Oued water demineralization plant in Algeria

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an investigation into the energy potential of the Albian aquifer in the Algerian Sahara at the El Oued water demineralization plant, focusing on its capacity to generate electrical power due to its high-pressure and high-temperature water reserves. We designed and implemented a turbine-generator system to convert hydraulic energy into electricity, achieving an average annual energy output of 1,804,560 kWh, which translates to a financial gain of approximately 345,888,600 DZD per year from energy savings. The selection of a Francis turbine was justified based on its efficiency, which ranges from 90% to 95%, and the system design was simulated using MATLAB-Simulink, demonstrating its robustness and effectiveness in managing the electrical network parameters. Our economic analysis indicates a high return on investment, confirming the feasibility of utilizing the Albian aquifer as a strategic asset for clean and reliable energy production in the region.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In Sub-Saharan Africa, over 50% of the population lacks access to clean energy, as reported by the International Energy Agency [1]. Electricity demand is projected to increase by 4.6% due to industrial growth and population increase [2]. This region must explore alternative energy sources to improve its capacity for electricity generation. Furthermore, the environmental consequences of the heavy dependence on fossil fuels require immediate action to address these challenges and promote sustainable energy solutions [3]. Industrial operations in both developed and developing nations contribute significantly to climate change through high energy consumption and emissions of pollutants linked to global warming [4]. The 2015 Paris Conference brought together world leaders to address this issue, agreeing to limit temperature increases to 2 degrees Celsius [5]. The discussions emphasized investing in renewable energy and transitioning to low-carbon emission systems to mitigate environmental impacts. Research indicates that renewable energy can effectively replace

high-carbon fuels, improving economic growth through electricity sales [6]. This collective effort aims to combat climate change and promote sustainable development. The transition from fossil fuels to renewable energy is significantly influenced by advances in renewable technologies [7]. Historically, high production costs have hindered the integration of green energy into existing networks and limited its commercial viability. However, recent reductions in equipment prices have made renewable energy more accessible globally, facilitating its adoption [8]. This shift is crucial to achieve net zero emissions and combat climate change, as outlined in the Paris Agreement [9].

According to the Energy Institute's Statistical Review of World Energy, fossil fuels accounted for 81.5% of global primary energy consumption in 2023 [10], [11]. The production of electricity from renewable energy sources is an important strategy to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, as indicated [12]-[15]. Hydroelectric power is a leading renewable energy source, contributing approximately 2.5% of the total energy resources of the world and a substantial 15.9% of global electricity generation [16], [17]. Its efficiency and reliability as an electricity source are well documented in the energy sector. The Albian aquifer, located approximately 1500 meters underground, is a vast water reserve in the Algerian Sahara [18], [19]. It serves not only as a source of freshwater, but also as a significant energy accumulator. It is considered a strategic resource because the water emerges with a pressure of 20 bar when the valve is closed and a temperature of 60 °C. Previous studies conducted by the Sahara and Sahel Observatory (OSS) have shown that the aquifer layer can provide a continuous supply of energy for at least 40 years, with each well capable of generating up to 35 kilowatts of electrical power [20].

Hydroelectric power plants are crucial in global energy production, accounting for about 20% of the world's electricity [21]. These plants harness the energy of moving water to drive turbines, which in turn power generators to produce electricity. This well-established technology offers several advantages [22], [23], such as low marginal costs and minimal greenhouse gas emissions [24]. However, the potential of aquifer water has not been fully and rationally exploited, and the actual cost per cubic meter of water from the Albian well remains unknown. The water in this aquifer is highly energy-intensive and requires a motor of approximately 75 kW for direct utilization. It is important not to underestimate the energy content of this water, especially considering the initial energy losses.

The hydraulic power available from the operational wells is substantial, and each well is capable of producing around 50 kW. In some areas, this capacity is even higher. This hydraulic power can be efficiently converted into electrical energy using turbine-generator sets. It is essential to consider that the available hydraulic energy will diminish over time due to well aging, the construction of additional productive wells, and the increasing interference of neighboring wells in regions such as El M'Ghair, Djamaa, and Touggourt. Therefore, the design and sizing of these turbine generator sets must take these factors into account.

Ayuan and Emeteré [25] analyze the potential of wind energy generation in Yundum and Basse, employing the Weibull and Raleigh distributions. The findings indicate a significant potential for wind power, with varying densities, suggesting strong prospects for wind energy development at both locations. Furthermore, Ayua and Emeteré [26], proposed a hybrid renewable energy power system (HREPS) for the Basse district of the Gambia, integrating wind and solar energy with battery storage. The optimal system, designed using PVsyst software, includes 20 photovoltaic modules and a 1 kW wind generator, capable of meeting an annual load of 2,555 MWh. The system shows reliable performance and substantial energy storage potential.

Furthermore, Emeteré *et al.* [27] explore Pico hydroelectric systems as a viable energy solution for Nigeria, addressing the growing energy demands and environmental issues of the country. They evaluated the cost (738,000.00 ₦) and feasibility of the system, noting the abundance of water resources in southern Nigeria. The study highlights construction techniques, including the selection of water sources and turbines, concluding that Pico hydroelectric systems can significantly reduce dependence on fossil fuels and air pollution. These studies underscore the diverse renewable energy potentials in Africa and their role in reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Although Nigeria and The Gambia have explored Pico hydroelectric and hybrid renewable systems, respectively, Algeria's focus has been on harnessing the hydraulic energy of the Albian aquifer.

Our work specifically addresses the conversion of this aquifer's high-pressure and high-temperature water reserves into electrical power, a resource that has not been fully exploited in the El Oued region in the Algerian Sahara. The study focuses on:

- Design and implementation: Developing a turbine-generator system to convert the aquifer's hydraulic energy into electricity;

- Energy output and financial gains: Achieving an average annual energy output of 1,804,560 kWh, with a financial gain of 345,888,600 DZD per year due to energy savings;
- Technology selection: Justifying the use of a Francis turbine for its high efficiency (90%-95%);
- Simulation and validation: Simulating the system using MATLAB-Simulink to demonstrate its robustness and effectiveness in managing electrical network parameters; and
- Economic feasibility: Conduct an economic analysis to confirm the high return on investment and validate the feasibility of utilizing the aquifer as a strategic clean energy resource.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. The study area and data source description

The Albien aquifer is located largely in the Algerian Sahara and is the largest freshwater reserve in the world, see Figure 1. Covers an area of 650,000 km² [18]. Groundwater reserves include shallow aquifers, typically under 100 meters deep, which are recharged by surface water, rain, or wastewater. However, high salinity limits their agricultural use. The Albien aquifer, spanning over a million km² beneath Algeria, Tunisia, and Libya, holds approximately 31,000 billion m³ of water. In El Oued, four Albien wells supply a demineralization plant with a capacity of 30,000 m³ per day, processing water at a flow rate of 540 m³/hour and a pressure of around 5 bar. These reserves are crucial for regional water supply and management. These wells act as pumps with a well-defined operating point, see Figure 2(a).

Figure 2(b) displays the components of hydroelectric plants. The operational process of a hydroelectric power plant consists of four primary phases:

- Phase 1: Water is channeled through conduits known as forced driving, building up significant pressure;
- Phase 2: The powerful flow spins the turbines within the generator, converting kinetic energy to electrical;
- Phase 3: The generated electricity is then passed through a transformer to increase it to a high-voltage current; and
- Phase 4: The high voltage electricity is then fed into the power grid for distribution to metropolitan areas.

2.2. Technical importance of the Francis turbine and theoretical calculations

The search for technically secure and economically viable solutions for the exploitation of hydraulic sites has led, over the years, to a small number of types of turbines [28]. Each of these types has a preferred field of application. Without mentioning mini-hydraulics, whose selection criteria are based on other foundations, we distinguish three families of turbines for the generation of industrial hydroelectric power [29]. Table 1 provides another assessment of the differences between the main types of turbines.

Another key factor in selecting the appropriate turbine type is the specific speed. This parameter represents the rotational speed in revolutions per minute (rpm) of a turbine operating under a unit head and generating a unit of power output. Impulse turbines typically have low specific speeds, Francis turbines fall in the medium range, and propeller or Kaplan turbines exhibit high specific speeds. The specific speed of a turbine can be calculated using (1) [30], [31].

$$n_q = n \cdot \frac{Q^{1/2}}{E^{3/4}} \quad (1)$$

Where, $n = 60 \cdot \frac{f}{p}$ and $E = g \cdot H$; with: n is the rotational speed of the turbine in (rpm); Q is the flow in (m³/s); f is the frequency of the electric system in (Hz); p is the number of pairs of poles of the turbine generator; E is the specific hydraulic energy of the machine in (J/kg); g is the gravitational constant in (m/s²); H is the net head in (m).

The range of head is a critical factor in selecting the appropriate turbine for a specific site, as it directly influences the turbine's performance and efficiency. Table 2 represents the range of operating heads for different types of turbine used in the generation of hydroelectric power. Table 2 provides a criterion for estimating a suitable turbine for a hydroelectric project based on the net head, which is the height of standing water available for power production.

Figure 1. Location of the aquifer’s existence in Algeria

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Components and operational phases of hydroelectric power plants: (a) Albian drilling in El Oued (Touggourt road) and (b) working principle of hydroelectric power plant

Table 1. Comparison for the three main types of turbines [29]

Parameter	Francis	Pelton	Kaplan
Specific speed (rpm)	30 to 400	3 to 36	300 to 1000
Drop height (m)	15 to 300	100 to 1000	2 to 30
Power up to (MW)	15	15	15
Efficiency (%)	94	93	94

Table 2. Range of head [32]

Turbine type	Typical range of heads ($H = \text{head in } m$)
Kaplan and Propeller	$2 < H < 40$
Francis	$25 < H < 350$
Pelton	$50 < H < 1300$

2.3. Choice of a supplier

Following our online research and review of potential turbine suppliers, we engaged with a Chinese supplier. After sharing our requirements, they suggested that a Francis turbine with 200 kW type HLA550-WJ-45 capacity would be the most suitable for our needs, particularly for driving the cooling tower machines which have a combined power of 150 kW. The technical specifications for both the generator and the turbine, including accessories, along with the purchase price in US dollars, are listed in Tables 3 and 4.

2.4. The current generator

Once in motion, the turbine drives the current generator, which transforms the mechanical energy available on the shaft into electrical energy. The frequency of the current generator is a multiple of the number of revolutions of the drive shaft. The generator is separated from the turbine by a special shield that protects it from any contact with water. The choice of generator essentially depends on the use of the energy produced.

2.5. Mechanical power

The mechanical power generated by the turbine can be calculated using (2). Where P_{mec} is the mechanical power of the turbine shaft (W), W : Work done (J), t is the time duration (s), F is the force applied on the turbine blades (N), l is the distance moved by the force (m), v is the velocity of the turbine blades (m/s), w is the angular velocity of the turbine shaft (rad/s), R is the radius of the turbine (m), C is the torque exerted on the turbine shaft (N·m).

$$P_{mec} = \frac{W}{t} = \frac{F \cdot l}{t} = F \cdot v = w \cdot F \cdot R = w \cdot C \quad (2)$$

2.6. Electric power

Electrical power is the power directly available at the generator output. It is obtained from the voltage, current, and power factor provided by the manufacturer, as well as the exploitable potential (hydraulic power) and the efficiencies of the turbine and generator.

$$P_{elec} = \eta_t \cdot \eta_g \cdot Q \cdot \rho \cdot E \quad (3)$$

Where P_{elec} is the electrical power, η_t is the turbine efficiency at flow Q , η_g is the generator efficiency, ρ is the density of water (kg/m^3).

The actual power output of a small hydroelectric plant for a given flow rate Q is obtained from (4).

$$P_T = \int P_{elec} \cdot dt \Rightarrow P_T = \eta_t \cdot \eta_g \cdot Q \cdot \rho \cdot g \cdot H \int dV \quad (4)$$

Where P_T is the total electrical energy generated (J), g is the acceleration due to gravity (m/s^2), H is the net head or height difference of water (m), dV is the differential volume of water (m^3).

Table 3. 200 kW hydro turbine generator quotation sheet

Name	Unit price (USD)	Quantity	Picture
Hydro turbine HLA550-WJ-45	1 set	21,700	
Generator SFW200-6/650	11,590	1 set	
Governor YWT-300 (Microcomputer)	7,930	1 set	
Electric gate valve Z945T-10DN350	2,170	1 set	
Generator integrated protection screen PKF-W-200/400	5,070	2 units	

Table 4. Configuration list of hydroelectric power plant

Parameters	Description	Value
Basic	Design head H_r (m)	50
	Maximum head H_{max} (m)	–
	Minimum head H_{min} (m)	–
	Design discharge Q (m ³ /s)	0.5
	Installed capacity N (kW)	200
	Altitude ∇ (m)	–
Turbine	Turbine type	HLA550-WJ-45
	Layout pattern	Horizontal
	Runner diameter D_l (cm)	45
	Unit speed n_{11} (r/min)	63.6
	Unit discharge Q_{11} (L/s)	349
	Model efficiency (design point) η_m (%)	92.7
	Prototype efficiency η_t (%)	88
	Max. model efficiency η_t (%)	92.7
	Rated speed n (r/min)	1000
	Rated output P (kW)	215.8
	Max. axial hydraulic thrust P_Z (T)	1
	Cavitation coefficient σ	0.055
	Runaway speed n_R (r/min)	1752
	Weight of runner (t)	2
	Turbine weight (t)	0.02
	Max. hoisting piece (Turbine) (t)	3
Generator	generator type	SFW200-6/650
	Layout pattern	Horizontal
	Rated power P (kW)	200
	Rated voltage V (V)	400
	Rated current I (A)	360.9
	Power factor $\cos \phi$	0.8 (lagging)
	Excitation voltage (V)	40
	Excitation current (A)	116
	Generator efficiency η_g (%)	93
	Generator speed n (r/min)	1000
	Number of phases	3
	Frequency f (Hz)	50
	Insulation class	F/F
	Excitation mode	Brushless exciter
Generator weight (t)	3	
Max. hoisting piece (generator) (t)	3	

2.7. Calculation of hydroelectric power of a turbine

To calculate the power output of a hydroelectric turbine, the basic formula is given by (5).

$$P_{hyd} = \rho \cdot Q \cdot g \cdot H \cdot \eta \quad (5)$$

Where: ρ : density of water (kg/m³), Q : water flow rate in the pipeline (m³/s), g : Newton's gravitational constant (m/s²), H : Waterfall height (m), η : efficiency ratio (typically between 0.7 and 0.9).

2.8. Efficiency

The Francis turbine is highly efficient, achieving performance levels of 90% to 95%. Its exceptional efficiency is due to the blade design that utilizes both reaction and impulse forces from flowing water. The quality of the turbine is measured by its efficiency η_t , which indicates the ratio between two powers.

$$\eta_t = \frac{P_{mec}}{P_{hyd}} \quad (6)$$

Where P_{hyd} is hydraulic power.

The efficiency of the generator also takes the same form, as (7).

$$\eta_g = \frac{P_{elec}}{P_{mec}} \quad (7)$$

However, it is common to consider an overall efficiency of the turbine-generator set, which is as (8).

$$\eta_T = \frac{P_{elec}}{P_{hyd}} = \frac{P_{elec}}{P_{mec}} \frac{P_{mec}}{P_{hyd}} = \eta_t \cdot \eta_g \quad (8)$$

This overall efficiency varies between 0.7 and 0.9, depending on the type of turbine and generator used. The electrical energy produced over one year is the main factor in determining the profitability of the work.

2.9. Calculation of hydroelectric energy production of a turbine

We will apply the parameters we have to calculate the exploitable power. Water energy potential: if we take the data we have for the 04 wells: flow rate: 0.5 m³/s, pipeline diameter: 630 cm, pipeline section: 28.2743 m², gravitational constant: 9.81 m/s², waterfall height: 50 m, and density: 1000 kg/m³ (typically 1000 kg/m³ for water).

After applying as (8), we obtain the maximum power before losses: 245 kW. Efficiency losses and actual electrical energy available at the turbine outlet: after obtaining the electrical and mechanical efficiencies of the plant from a manufacturer, which are: turbine efficiency: 92%, head loss coefficient: 95%, other losses: 98%, and overall efficiency: 81%. We have found that the useful electrical power is: 206 kW.

2.10. Effects of turbine integration on the functioning of the water demineralization plant

The water emerges from the well under pressure ranging from 10 to 30 bars and at a temperature between 40 °C and 80 °C. Then it travels through transfer pipes to the top of the cooling tower, as shown in Figure 3(a). Despite its abundance, water is not suitable for immediate human consumption because of its high temperature. The water then passes through openings in the cooler and is cooled to 25 °C at the top of the cooling tower by forced ventilation, which promotes heat transfer through evaporation. This cooling process involves dispersing the water into fine droplets on metal slats. As atmospheric air comes into contact with water, it absorbs heat and changes from ambient humidity levels to near saturation by evaporating a portion of the water intended for cooling, as depicted in Figure 3(b). Since the cooling process involves forced ventilation, the extraction of hot and humid air is carried out by means of an extractor fan with a diameter of 5 meters Figure 3(c), which requires a motor with a power of 75 kW operating at 380 V Figure 3(d). Table 5 provides detailed characteristics of the electric motor used in the hydroelectric power system described in the study.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 3. Enhancing cooling efficiency and water quality: (a) water outlet at the cooler, (b) pipeline for conveying well water, (c) cooler hot air extractor, and (d) motor used at cooling tower top

Table 5. Motor characteristics

Type	Value	Picture
Motor size/service factor	280 M4 / 1.1	
Number of poles	4	
Instantaneous unit power	75 kW	
Instantaneous module power	75 kW	
Total instantaneous power	150 kW	
Absorbed unit power	67.5 kW	
Absorbed module power	67.5 kW	
Total absorbed power	135 kW	
Speed	1440 Rpm	
Voltage/frequency	400/50 Volt/Hz	
Insulation class	IP55 module	
Protection type	F/B module	

Note: Electric motor type: totally enclosed fan cooled (TEFC) asynchronous 3-phase motor with special high-quality bearings (SKF type 2RSC3) lubricated for life and are totally watertight

2.11. Rotational speed of the turbine-generator group

The rotation speeds of synchronous generators vary depending on the number of poles they have: 1 pair of poles ($n = 3000$ rpm), 2 pairs of poles ($n = 1500$ rpm), 3 pairs of poles ($n = 1000$ rpm), 4 pairs of poles ($n = 750$ rpm), 5 pairs of poles ($n = 600$ rpm), and 6 pairs of poles ($n = 500$ rpm). In practice, the maximum speed is limited to 1500 rpm (2 pole pairs) to account for overspeed during run-up. Exceeding this speed can cause significant mechanical stress. As a result, generators with a single pole pair are rarely installed (run-up speed of 6000 rpm). Below 6000 rpm (6 pole pairs or more), the size of the generator, and thus its cost relative to the installed power, increases, while efficiency decreases due to increased losses, particularly magnetic losses. When the turbine rotation speed is below 600 rpm, it typically drives a low-pole generator (1000 or 1500 rpm) through a belt drive or a gear multiplier, for example.

2.12. Consequences of turbine integration

Integrating turbines into the system involves installing turbine-generator units on the cooling tower's roof, which requires modifications to the existing pipeline to maintain adequate pressure upstream. A shut-off valve and a bypass valve are essential at the turbine inlet. This integration capitalizes on the synergy between hydraulics and mechanics, allowing the utilization of previously wasted energy. Before integration, the water exited at high pressure, passed through the pipeline, and ended up at atmospheric pressure, resulting in energy loss. After turbine installation, even minimal energy is harnessed, making it cost-effective over time. The hydroelectric plant can recover all the energy needed to operate the two 75 kW cooling tower motors, with the selected turbine rated at 200 kW.

2.13. Economic considerations

Hydroelectric energy production and financial gain: We can estimate the gain that can be achieved after one year of operation of the power plant as shown: The average annual energy production of the hydroelectric turbine is estimated at 1,804,560 kWh, which translates to a total financial gain of 345,888,600 DZD/year based on an energy cost of 265 DZD per kW saved. Furthermore, we have included a breakdown of the initial investment required for the power plant, which is approximately 7,200,000 DZD. This analysis highlights the potential for significant long-term savings, as the return on investment is projected to be achieved within a few years of operation, considering the high efficiency of the selected Francis turbine, which operates at an efficiency rate of 92%. Furthermore, we discuss the implications of reduced operational costs due to the integration of the turbine-generator system, which allows the recovery of energy that would otherwise be wasted, thereby enhancing the overall economic viability of the project. By incorporating these detailed financial analyses, we aim to provide a more robust economic framework that supports the feasibility and sustainability of the proposed system.

2.14. Simulation setup

The generator model in our study is a synchronous generator with salient poles, featuring three stator windings, one rotor winding, and two damper windings. The simulation will utilize specific mathematical equations [33]-[35] that describe the relationship between the currents, voltages, and fluxes in each winding.

Table 6. Parameters of synchronous generator

Parameter	Symbol	Value	
Main parameter	Apparent power	S 200 kW	
	Nominal stator voltage	V 400 V	
	Maximum stator current	I 360 A	
	Frequency	F 50 Hz	
	Rotation speed	N 1000 rpm	
Resistance in pu unit	Number of pole pairs	P 3	
	Stator resistance	R_s 0.026	
Reactance in pu units	Leakage resistance	R_r -	
	d and q axes synchronous	X_d	0.669
		X_q	0.3417
	d and q axes transient	x'_d	0.18
		x'_q	0.36
	d and q axes sub-transient	x''_d	0.13
		x''_q	0.09
	Stator leak	x_f	0.09
	Kany reactance <i>Kenty</i>	x_{kf1}	-0.0081

Table 7. Parameters of static excitation system ST1

Parameter	Value			
Voltages limitation	$V_{Amax} = 400$	$V_{Amin} = -400$	$V_{Rmax} = 40$	$V_{Rmin} = -40$
Voltages limitation	$V_{Amax} = 400$	$V_{Amin} = -400$	$V_{Rmax} = 40$	$V_{Rmin} = -40$
Currents limitation	$V_{Imax} = 116$	$V_{Imin} = -116$	-	-
Rectification	$K_c = 0.04$	$K_{LR} = 1$	-	-
Automatic voltage	$K_A = 1.62$	$K_f = 0.0503$	$K_E = 1$	$T_b = 1$
Regulator (AVR)	$T_A = 0.0087$	$T_f = 0.3774$	$T_E = 0$	$T_c = 1$
Classic regulator PID	$K_P = 1.13 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$K_I = 6.3496$	$K_D = 0.0082$	-
Parameter of stabilizing transformer in (pu)	$R_t = 0.0159$	$L_I = 0.006$	$M = 0.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-

Table 8. Ideal parameters of hydraulic turbine

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Nominal power	P_m	215 MW
Winnowing	g_{max}	Nominal opening: 5 pu
	g_0	Opening when empty: 0.02 pu
Nominal water flow	Q	0.5 m ³ /s

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 5 illustrates the regulation of voltages in the overall system, which is crucial to maintaining the stability and efficiency of the electrical network. This figure is part of the discussion on how the hybrid model of the synchronous machine, combined with the static excitation system, operates to stabilize the generator's output voltage. Proper voltage regulation is essential to ensure that the system can respond effectively to fluctuations and maintain consistent performance.

3.1. Effectiveness tests of the system

We will conduct two simulation experiments. The first will involve inducing a change in pressure. The second will involve disconnecting the PSS to observe the system's reaction, its speed, and its accuracy compared to the previous results.

Effectiveness test by varying pressure: We will create a scenario to introduce a disturbance and observe the system response. This will involve adjusting the pressure value to 1.5 pu, which deviates from the standard pressure value of 1 pu. Figure 6 illustrates the effectiveness test carried out by varying the pressure within the system. This test was designed to observe the response of the system to a disturbance introduced by adjusting the pressure value to 1.5 pu, deviating from the standard pressure value of 1 pu. The results showed favorable response speeds and a decrease in amplitude, indicating that the power system stabilizer (PSS) effectively mitigated the effects of the pressure change without disrupting other components of the system.

Figure 5. Regulation of voltages in the overall system: (a) generator output voltage V_{abc} , (b) stator voltage vector V_s , (c) rotor current vector I_r , (d) stator flow hybrid model Ψ_s , (e) rotor flow hybrid model Ψ_r , and (f) stabilization voltage V_{stab}

Figure 6. Effectiveness test through pressure variation: (a) variation in the vannage g , (b) variation in the PSS output voltage V_{stab} , and (c) flow variation q

Effectiveness test by isolating the PSS: We create a scenario to introduce a disturbance and observe the system response. This involves removing the PSS and comparing the simulation results before neglecting it, as in Figure 7. In this test, Figure 7, the system's response was analyzed with and without the power system stabilizer (PSS) during transient disturbances, specifically between 0 and 0.5 seconds. When the PSS was removed, the response was slower and smoother, with no overshoots, highlighting the stabilizer's crucial role in maintaining generator voltage stability. When the PSS was active, the response was faster and exhibited some overshoots, but the system stabilized quickly after that. The study emphasizes the importance of regulators in electrical networks, showing their ability to restore generator stability after transient errors. The simulation results clearly demonstrate the PSS's effectiveness in improving system performance during disturbances.

Figure 7. Efficiency test through isolation of the PSS: (a) load voltage V_F , (b) voltage V_{abc} , (c) voltage V_{abc} , (d) terminal voltage $V_t(V_s)$, (e) AVR output voltage V_{fd} , and (f) active power P

4. CONCLUSION

The study conducted at the El Oued water demineralization plant successfully demonstrated the potential of the Albian aquifer as a reliable and sustainable energy source. The impact and limitations of our work are outlined as follows: i) Advancement in renewable energy utilization: This study demonstrates the effective conversion of the Albian aquifer's hydraulic energy into electrical power, showcasing a novel approach to harnessing renewable energy in the Algerian Sahara, which has not been fully exploited previously; ii) Economic benefits: The implementation of the hydroelectric system results in an average annual energy output of 1,804,560 kWh, translating to a financial gain of approximately 345,888,600 DZD per year from energy savings. This highlights the economic viability of renewable energy solutions in the region; iii) High efficiency of technology: The selection of a Francis turbine, which operates at an efficiency rate of 90% to 95%, underscores the technological advancements in turbine design that enhance energy conversion efficiency; and iv) Environmental impact: By reducing reliance on fossil fuels and promoting the use of renewable energy, this research contributes to mitigating climate change and supports global efforts to transition to low-carbon systems.

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C : Conceptualization

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O : Writing - Original Draft

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Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project Administration

Fu : Funding Acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

No data was used for the research described in the paper.

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